

Contending for the Faith: Substantiating the Reality of God

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*The statements made in this research paper represent the opinions of the author.

Author's Biography

Dr. Winfred Wills is an avid, Christian researcher. He earned a Bachelor of Science (B.S.) in Education in 2003 from Salisbury University; a Master of Education (M.Ed.) in 2009 from Strayer University; a Doctorate of Biblical Counseling (D.B.C.) from Oval Bible College in 2012; and an Educational Specialist Certificate (Ed.S.) in 2014 from Argosy University. He has been awarded multiple grants to further his research, and continues to dedicate himself to the highest standards of scholarship in his Religious Scientific Research.

Abstract:

This research paper is a qualitative analysis of a combination of religious and scientific studies in response to the atheistic contention that God does not exist. Analysis of this combined body of literature makes a circumstantial case for God. While no piece of evidence by itself acts as direct evidence, the combination in its totality proves by inference that God is the only rational explanation for life as we know it. One finding is that abiogenesis or life arising from nonliving material has been demonstrated impossible both experimentally and mathematically. Therefore, the cause of life would have to be a living being who is all powerful. Giving credence to this conclusion is the occurrence of two miraculous healings that could not have happened without God. Two different peer-reviewed, medical journals confirmed the truth that two people who had been afflicted with life long, incurable illnesses were healed miraculously and spontaneously by proximal intercessory prayer. Doctors and scientists have no definitive explanation for the occurrence and have gone a step further in declaring the prayer and healing relationship futile to research any further. This indicates that science has no explanation for these miracles and is aware that the forming thereof is impossible. Hence, by deduction, this would constitute divine intervention, which is not possible unless God is real. Moreover, the testimony of former atheists that their knowledge of science and reason did not complete their lives as they felt something was missing alludes to the reality of God. These people reported that they had needs that nothing could fulfill until they met God. When people speak in reference to a need, they reference something that is necessary for survival. The fact that they referenced God in such a way stands as more evidence that He is real.

Introduction

An anonymous philosopher once said of truth that it “Can be likened to a master key by virtue of its power to unlock multiple doors.” The message here was that an understanding of what is legitimate and correct has a special strength, one capable of helping us escape the confining nature of misinformation. In the atheist community, many are in bondage from being misinformed. The evidence of this is the belief that everything has a natural explanation that makes God unnecessary. Adding to the lack of accuracy is the imprecise assumption that a lack of direct evidence for God’s presence is proof that He does not exist. Instead, the atheist restricts his or her beliefs about reality to that which is measurable and observable. Furthermore, while the atheist seeks direct evidence that God is real, circumstantial evidence, which proves truth by way of inference, leads to the conclusion of His undeniable reality.

When examining the evidence for God’s presence, one must consider that while each fact alone may not “prove” God’s existence, they create an ironclad and compelling case for God when taken as a whole. Firstly, abiogenesis or life arising from nonlife is impossible as demonstrated both experimentally and mathematically. This means that by deduction, it took a living being to create life as we know it. Additionally, the conduction and publication of studies in reputable, peer-reviewed, medical journals show with certainty that contrary to the atheist contention, events requiring God’s divine intervention do take place. Moreover, former atheists who have converted to Christianity have all expressed a variation of the theme that there was a void in their lives that they could not communicate. This void remained unfilled until they came to the knowledge of God. It is this body of evidence, which by way of inference establishes the reality of spiritual life and the truth of God’s presence.

Abiogenesis is Experimentally and Mathematically Impossible**The History of the 1800's Anti-Religious Movement**

In the 1800s, an anti-religion movement began to take place. Darwin's science began to be used to argue against theism (McKenna, 2024). Additionally, this period of history saw an increase in anti-religious, skeptical literature. In 1859, Darwin published a work known as *On the Origin of the Species* (19th Century Free Thinkers, 2024). It was argued by Darwin that species evolved naturally over time via random selection. Further asserted by Darwin was that life formed spontaneously in a "primordial soup" which contained all the building blocks for life, namely carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur.

Experimental Results Suggest the Impossibility of Abiogenesis

For Darwin's contention to be true, life would have to be able to come from nonlife. In 1859, Louis Pasteur, who doubted Darwin's idea that life could spontaneously generate from nonlife, conducted an experiment designed to test this notion. According to Britannica (2024) "He showed that beef broth could be sterilized by boiling it in a "swan-neck" flask, which has a long bending neck that traps dust particles and other contaminants before they reach the body of the flask." Pasteur kept the flasks sealed for one full year. At the end of this time, there was no evidence of any life nor anything that gave an indication that it was moving in the direction of generating life. Life's most basic building blocks, carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur, are present in all living things (Where Do Life's Building Blocks Come From, 2024). Hence, it stands to reason that all of these things would have to be present in the beef broth. Thus, the experiment demonstrated that these elements together could not generate life and disproved Darwin's notion once and for all.

This left a problem for the atheistic community, who needed life to be able to arise from nonlife in order for Darwin's theory of Natural Creation and Evolution to be true. In 1870, Thomas Huxley coined the term abiogenesis (Colman, 2015). It was his assertion that Louis Pasteur proved that complex life arising from nonlife could not happen in today's atmosphere, and he referred to this idea as Spontaneous Generation. Instead, he proposed that abiogenesis or life arising from nonlife was possible under the conditions of the prebiotic earth and ceased to be possible under today's atmospheric conditions. Then, in 1952, Drs. Urey and Miller conducted an experiment in which they attempted to mimic the conditions of the early earth inside of an apparatus, passed lightning through the apparatus, and found that amino acids were formed (Aker et al, 2024). This was hailed by the atheist community as proof that Huxley's hypothesis was likely correct as amino acids are the building blocks of life.

To many this seemed straightforward in suggesting a real possibility of life arising naturally. However, there were many problems with both Thomas Huxley's assertions and the Urey-Miller experimental results, rendering them inapplicable and lacking probative value. Regarding Huxley's hypothesis, the atmosphere with its oxygen content would render the formation of life impossible. Earth's earliest atmosphere contained more free oxygen than scientists have previously calculated (Bracewell, 2005).

In a recent study, air bubbles trapped in salt crystals in a rock unit supposedly 815 million years old in western central Australia were analyzed. These air bubbles were assumed to represent the atmospheric air at the time the bubbles got trapped in the salt crystals. That assumption was tested and verified, at least for modern conditions, by analyzing air bubbles trapped in salt crystals forming today in salty ponds and lakes. The study results were very surprising, at least for the uniformitarian (evolutionary) scientists.

The air in these bubbles had an average oxygen content of 10.9%, which is slightly more than 50% PAL! To put that into perspective, this means oxygen was very abundant in the earth's [early] atmosphere. (Snelling, 2016, par. 5).

With respect to the Urey-Miller Experiment, its value has been overstated in history books and the atheist community alike. It is true that amino acids formed in this experiment. However, they were an even mix of left and right handed amino acids, which would have made protein formation impossible (Houts, 2024). Without proteins, there could be no life. Despite these facts, which the scientist community has to know about, many continue to hail these results as being demonstrative of how life may have come about naturally; a conclusion totally contradicted by the results.

The Miller–Urey experiments involved filling a sealed glass apparatus with the gasses that Oparin had speculated were necessary to form life—namely methane, ammonia and hydrogen (to mimic the conditions that they thought were in the early atmosphere) and water vapor (to simulate the ocean). Next, while a heating coil kept the water boiling, they struck the gasses in the flask with a high-voltage (60,000 volts) tungsten spark-discharge device to simulate lightning. Below this was a water-cooled condenser that cooled and condensed the mixture, allowing it to fall into a water trap below. Within a few days, the water and gas mix produced a pink stain on the sides of the flask trap. As the experiment progressed and the chemical products accumulated, the stain turned deep red, then turbid. After a week, the researchers analyzed the substances in the U-shaped water trap used to collect the reaction products. The primary substances in the gaseous phase were carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrogen (N₂). The dominant solid material was an insoluble toxic carcinogenic mixture called

‘tar’ or ‘resin’, a common product in organic reactions, including burning tobacco (Bergman, 2022).

Moreover, the Urey-Miller Experiment was flawed in multiple ways, making it irrelevant to the origins of life. According to Bracewell (2005) who cited the work of *The Collapse of Evolution*, by Scott M. Huse, Ph.D. p. 153;

1. The concentrations of methane and ammonia were carefully selected to ensure the production of organic molecules. There is no evidence to suggest the Earth’s atmosphere was so characterized.
2. There is no evidence to indicate the Earth’s early atmosphere was reducing. There is, however, considerable evidence to suggest the Earth had an oxidizing atmosphere during most, if not all, of its history.
3. A methane-ammonia-reducing atmosphere would be fatal to life-forms.
4. The simulation of lightning by mild spark discharges is unrealistic. Actual lightning would have destroyed any organics that may have been present.
5. The molecules produced in the Miller-Urey apparatus would react detrimentally to life forms that were trying to evolve. Chemically, they would destroy all hope of producing life.

The other problems with the experiment are as follows:

1. They cheated. They designed the apparatus to separate amino acids from the mix once they were formed. If they hadn’t done that as soon as an amino acid was formed, the next electrical spark may have rearranged the atoms into some other form.

2. The amino acids they did produce were half left-handed and half right-handed, just like you would expect from a random process like electrical sparks in a gas mixture. The trouble is, only left-handed amino acids are used in organisms.
3. Additional molecules were formed other than amino acids. Namely, formaldehyde and cyanide, which are destructive to life. (Bracewell, 2005).

Abiogenesis Has Been Calculated at Impossible Based on Theoretical Probability

In addition to the experiments, which suggest that abiogenesis cannot happen, it has also been calculated mathematically as being impossible. Omerbasic (2021) and Creager (2023) concur with Borel's Law, that at a probability of 1 in 10 to the 50th power, the event is deemed impossible from a statistical standpoint. Omerbasic, through the use of the 574 amino acids that comprise hemoglobin and the 20 different amino acids comprising the human body calculated the theoretical probability that even a hemoglobin molecule could evolve from inanimate material by random chance at 1 in 10 to the 1092nd power. This is 1042 exponential powers below what statisticians deem impossible.

Complementing Omerbasic's research was Creager (2023). In his calculations, Creager examined a life form that needed the bare minimum 438 genes in order to sustain life.

According to Creager's calculations:

“Given the fact that each amino acid is encoded for by three base pairs, a 50 amino acid protein would require 150 base pairs consisting of 4 possible nucleotides resulting in 4^{150} or 2×10^{90} , possible combinations, this means that the odds against getting any particular protein encoded by the DNA are 1 in 2×10^{90} (150/531,490) or 1 in 5.75×10^{86} . However, you have to do this 438 times resulting in the odds of encoding all of the amino acids being 1 in 5×10^{38000} . When this is combined with the odds of getting all functional

proteins to begin with, we get odds of 1 in 5×10^{38000} [multiplied by] 3.6×10^{24550} or 1 in 1.8×10^{62551} [essentially a probability of 1 in infinity]. This shows that the odds of getting just this much are statistically impossible, and it doesn't include further assembly of the various proteins into a functioning system.” (Creager, 2023, Par. 6)

While the atheist would argue that statistical impossibility is a high degree of improbability versus absolute impossibility which means something cannot happen at all, there is a flaw in this interpretation. The first interpretation only applies in cases where all known outcomes are confirmed to be based on real possibilities. When referencing possibilities that have never been observed and may be imaginary, statistically impossible is an indication that the event is likely to be absolutely impossible. Furthermore, at a probability of 1 in infinity, one has arrived mathematically as close to absolute impossibility as one can get without being able to observe the event. From this, the logical conclusion is that abiogenesis is absolutely impossible.

Miracles that Could Only Happen By Divine Intervention

In addition to the impossibility of abiogenesis, two cases of miraculous healing were studied and verified as true by two reputable, peer-reviewed, medical journals; *The Journal of Complementary Medicine* and *Explore*, respectively. In *The Journal of Complementary Medicine*, a reported case was that of a man who had suffered from gastroparesis, a condition that stops or significantly slows food down in its passage from the stomach to the small intestine, from his birth (Romez et al, 2019). At the age of 16, the patient could no longer tolerate oral feedings and in 1995, he became dependent on tube feedings. After attending proximal-intercessory prayer at a church, he reported feeling a sensation of electric shock go from his shoulder to his stomach. After this, his condition resolved and the patient experienced complete healing. Furthermore, the doctors in this study concluded that it was virtually

impossible that this could be explained by the placebo effect. This is due to the fact that the placebo effect is incapable of curing any condition, only providing temporary symptom relief. No doctor has been able to give a definitive explanation as to the reason why this unprecedented healing took place, and it is doubtful that any doctor or scientist ever will as this healing has no root in scientific medicine, it is unheard of, unprecedented, and impossible absent divine intervention.

The next miraculous case was reported in *Explore: Journal of Science and Healing*, another reputable, scientific, peer-reviewed journal. A woman aged 18, was declared legally blind due to macular degeneration in 1960 (Romez et al, 2021). In 1972, after proximal-intercessory prayer, she spontaneously regained her eyesight. As of the time this study was conducted, her eyesight has remained stable. Once more, the doctors found the placebo or Hawthorne effects relatively impossible for explaining this miracle. Additionally, they have conceded that there is no absolute or definitive scientific explanation for this spontaneous regaining of sight following this proximal-intercessory prayer to God in the name of Jesus. Given that such attempts to explain this scientifically have been tried unsuccessfully in the past, it is practically certain that there will ever be a scientific explanation. This type of healing is way outside of scientific parameters and is not scientific in nature. Some professionals in the scientific community have taken the added step of conceding that any further study of this phenomenon would be useless in terms of scientific advancement (Andrade & Radhakrishnan, 2009).

Former Atheists Who Became Believers

Jana Harmon, a researcher, conducted a study in which she interviewed fifty former atheists who agreed to share what it was that caused them to renounce atheism. The theme that

came up repeatedly was feeling instinctively as though something was missing, which prompted a search for something greater than one's worldview (Reese, 2023). Intrinsically, the majority of former atheists in this study understood that their worldviews were limiting in so many respects. They were therefore compelled by something that they could not explain, to search for that absent piece. In spite of their unbelief, they were persuaded that there had to be more. This reported instinct demonstrates that humans are spiritual beings by virtue of their longing for God even at a time when they were doubtful of His existence.

Another example of this theme was seen in the case of Mrs. Jennifer Fulweiler, who reported being born into an atheist family and not even believing in God as a child. She described her life, growing up as being a diet of reason and belief in what was provable and observable (Atheist to Christian Testimony, 2014). She reported that the birth of her child changed her and caused her to feel like there had to be something more to life; something she was missing. In her own words, it was an overwhelming, instinctive feeling that [her] love for [her] child and the strength of their bond could not be "mere random chemical reactions." This prompted her to begin investigating religious concepts. When she began studying Christianity and other world religions, she was not completely persuaded at first. So, she decided to put out every question she considered hard. As stated by Fulweiler (2014) "Christians and atheists had the scientific concepts correct, yet the Christian responses more accurately portrayed the human experience." As a result, she became compelled to believe in the Christian faith despite its being initially counterintuitive. Similar to participants in the aforementioned study, she knew intrinsically that there was more to life than what science offered in the way of explanation.

Conclusions

All things taken into account, this body of evidence in its totality makes a powerful case for God. Primarily, the theory of abiogenesis or life arising from nonlife, despite its acceptance by the scientific community, is very obviously lacking accuracy as it is backed by an experiment that was manipulated and produced more elements that would be toxic to life than actual amino acids. Moreover, the impossibility of abiogenesis was proven by two researchers mathematically, one of whom placed the chance at 1 in infinity, the closest one can get to absolute impossibility. These factors combined demonstrate that the only way life could have come to be is through a living source. Given all information, this living source is a spiritual life form that is all powerful, God.

Further making the case for God's existence is the occurrence of miraculous events that would be impossible without His direct, divine intervention. The fact that two reputable, medical, peer-reviewed journals validated these miracles stands as testimony of their truth and accuracy. In one case, a man was cured of a life-long, incurable stomach ailment by way of proximal-intercessory prayer. The other instance was one in which a woman was cured of blindness by this same means after losing her eyesight to macular degeneration twelve years earlier. Reputable medical doctors, who reported experiencing similar miracles in their careers, said that further scientific study of the prayer and healing relationship would lack meaningful purpose. One can rightly infer that the rationale has to do with the lack of a definitive explanation for these supernatural occurrences on the part of the scientific community. In fact, the concession by members of their own community that because it is outside the scope of anything scientific, the odds of a natural explanation existing in the future lack a real possibility. The connection here between the all powerful being that created life as we know it and the

miraculous healing is evident. Just like it took an almighty God to create life, it was this same power that He utilized to heal these people of their infirmities, once more establishing the reality of his presence circumstantially.

Additional evidence for the reality of God is in the testimony of those who did not believe He was real at first and later renounced this notion. This resulted from these people inherently craving a relationship with a being greater than themselves, yet lacked the words for describing such a longing. What are the chances that all of these people would come up with some version of the same theme and there be no truth to it? Proven by these facts is that humans are spiritual beings and that God communicates with them spiritually. That longing through their initial disbelief was God speaking to them, letting them know that He was indeed real. After all, all of the former atheists interviewed concluded that nothing other than God could fill this void in their lives regardless of the length of time their atheism lasted.

While the atheist community continues to argue that God is neither proved nor disproved, this body of evidence tells a much different story. He is proved by the combined totality of these established facts. Knowing all that we know, can the atheist really rule out the existence of a spiritual life form? Are scientists not constantly discovering new life forms? Have there not been discoveries of life forms scientists did not believe existed until they were discovered? Objectively assessing the theist and the atheist leads to one fundamental difference, the true meaning of “proof.” Theists accept circumstantial evidence and the establishment of truth via inference. Atheists on the other hand insist on direct evidence. Yet and still, taken as a whole, this body of knowledge indicates with certainty that God is very real.

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